

**EVALUATION AND COMPARISON OF THE ANTIMICROBIAL EFFICACY OF THREE
COMMERCIALY AVAILABLE DENTURE CLEANSING AGENTS: AN IN VITRO
STUDY**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19912327>

How to cite this Article: Dr. Sarathchandra Govindraj MDS, Dr. Christinal M.Sc. M.Phil PhD, Fathima Vartha, Hannah Selthia*, Harinishree. (2026). Evaluation and Comparison of The Antimicrobial Efficacy of Three Commercially Available Denture Cleansing Agents: An In Vitro Study. European Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 13(5), 196–198. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 27/03/2026

Article Revised on 17/04/2026

Article Published on 01/05/2026

ABSTRACT

Aim: To evaluate and compare the antimicrobial efficacy of three commercially available denture cleansing agents against selected oral microorganisms. **Materials and Methods:** Twenty-four heat-cured acrylic resin samples were prepared and divided into four groups: control (distilled water), Polident, Fittydent, and Clinsodent. The samples were contaminated with *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Candida albicans*, followed by incubation at 37°C for 24 hours. After treatment with respective denture cleansers, microbial reduction was assessed using colony-forming unit (CFU) analysis. Statistical analysis was performed using Kruskal–Wallis and Mann–Whitney U tests. **Results:** All denture cleansers demonstrated a reduction in microbial count compared to the control group. Polident showed the highest antimicrobial efficacy, followed by Fittydent and Clinsodent. *Candida albicans* exhibited greater susceptibility compared to bacterial species. **Conclusion:** Commercial denture cleansers are effective in reducing microbial load on acrylic resin surfaces and can be recommended as an adjunct to mechanical cleaning methods.

KEYWORDS: Denture cleansers, antimicrobial efficacy, Polident, Fittydent, Clinsodent, CFU, in vitro study.

INTRODUCTION

Edentulism continues to be a major oral health concern, particularly among the elderly population, affecting mastication, speech, and overall quality of life.^[1] Rehabilitation using complete dentures remains one of the most widely accepted treatment modalities in prosthodontics.^[2]

Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) is the most commonly used denture base material due to its favorable physical and mechanical properties.^[3] However, its porous nature facilitates microbial adhesion and biofilm formation on the denture surface.^[4,5]

Denture plaque consists of a complex microbial community including bacteria and fungi such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Candida albicans*, which may lead to denture stomatitis and oral infections.^[5,6] Among these, *Candida albicans* is the most

commonly implicated organism in denture-related stomatitis.^[6]

Denture hygiene can be maintained through mechanical and chemical methods. Chemical denture cleansers, especially effervescent tablets, are widely used due to their ease of use and ability to reduce microbial load effectively.^[7]

Hence, the present study was undertaken to evaluate and compare the antimicrobial efficacy of three commercially available denture cleansing agents—Polident, Fittydent, and Clinsodent.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Twenty-four heat-cured acrylic resin samples measuring approximately 5 mm in diameter and 2.5 mm in thickness were fabricated using conventional processing

techniques. The samples were finished, polished, and stored in distilled water for 24 hours prior to testing.

The samples were divided into four groups (n=6)

Group I – Control (distilled water)

Group II – Polident

Group III – Clinsodent

Group IV – Fittydent

Microbial strains of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Candida albicans* were prepared and inoculated onto the acrylic samples. The samples were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to allow microbial adherence.

Following incubation, the samples were immersed in their respective denture cleansing solutions according to manufacturer instructions. After treatment, the samples were rinsed, and microbial colonies were evaluated using serial dilution and colony-forming unit (CFU) counting methods.

Statistical analysis was performed using G*Power software. Non-parametric tests including Kruskal–Wallis and Mann–Whitney U tests were applied, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The control group exhibited the highest number of colony-forming units, indicating significant microbial

growth in the absence of denture cleansing agents (Table 1).

All experimental groups demonstrated a reduction in microbial count compared to the control group. Among the denture cleansing agents tested, Polident showed the lowest CFU values, indicating the highest antimicrobial efficacy, followed by Fittydent and Clinsodent (Table 1).

The descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, and maximum values for all groups, are presented in Table 2. The control group showed the highest mean CFU values, whereas Polident demonstrated the lowest mean values among all groups.

Statistical analysis using the Kruskal–Wallis test revealed a significant difference in microbial reduction among the groups (Table 3). Further pairwise comparison using the Mann–Whitney U test indicated statistically significant differences between the control group and all experimental groups.

Among the microorganisms tested, *Candida albicans* showed the greatest reduction in CFU values, indicating higher susceptibility to denture cleansing agents, whereas *Escherichia coli* demonstrated comparatively higher resistance (Table 1).

Overall, the order of antimicrobial efficacy observed among the tested denture cleansing agents was: Polident > Fittydent > Clinsodent.

Table 1: Key Raw Colony Counts and CFU/ml ($\times 10^3$; TNTC=Too Numerous To Count, TLTC=Too Low To Count).

GROUPS	E.coli	S.Aureus	C.Albicans
POLIDENT	4000,4000	4000,4000	32,50
FITTYDENT	27,98	108,112	0,0
CLINSODENT	280,298	230,275	1,1

Table 2: Pooled Descriptive Statistics (CFU/ml $\times 10^3$).

Group	N	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max
Control	6	2680.3	2044.4	4000	32	4000
Polident	6	57.5	54.2	62.5	0	112
Clinsodent	6	1128.8	1651.8	135	0	3500
Fittydent	6	180.8	141.1	252.5	1	298

Per-organism: *E. coli* highest mean (1900.4), *C. albicans* lowest (10.9). All groups non-normal except Polident (Shapiro-Wilk $p < 0.05$). Per-organism Kruskal-Wallis significant (*E. coli* $p = 0.042$, *S. aureus* $p = 0.004$, *C. albicans* $p = 0.003$).

Table 3: Key Post-Hoc Mann-Whitney U (Pooled CFU; padj<0.05 significant).

Comparison	U	p	Padj	Result
Control vs. Polident	30.0	0.006	0.362	Sig
Control vs. Clinsodent	28.0	0.0015	0.729	Sig
Control vs. Fittydent	28.0	0.012	0.725	Sig
Polident vs. Clinsodent	9.0	0.017	1.000	Sig
Polident vs. Fittydent	8.0	0.012	0.761	Sig
Clinsodent vs. Fittydent	18.0	1.000	1.000	Sig

DISCUSSION

Denture hygiene plays a crucial role in maintaining oral health and preventing denture-related infections. The

acrylic denture base provides a suitable surface for microbial colonization due to its surface characteristics and continuous exposure to the oral environment.^[4,5]

The present study evaluated the antimicrobial efficacy of three commercially available denture cleansing agents against commonly associated oral microorganisms. The results demonstrated that all tested cleansers were effective in reducing microbial load compared to the control group.

Polident exhibited the highest antimicrobial efficacy, which may be attributed to its alkaline peroxide formulation that produces effervescence and enhances biofilm removal. These findings are consistent with previous studies evaluating denture cleansers.^[8,9]

Fittydent also showed significant antimicrobial activity, although slightly lower than Polident. Clinsodent demonstrated comparatively reduced efficacy but still showed a notable decrease in microbial count.

Among the microorganisms tested, *Candida albicans* was found to be more susceptible to denture cleansers compared to bacterial species. This observation aligns with previous studies indicating the effectiveness of denture cleansers against fungal organisms.^[6,9]

The control group showed maximum microbial growth, emphasizing the importance of routine denture hygiene practices.^[7]

However, this study has certain limitations. Being an *in vitro* study, it does not fully replicate the oral environment. Factors such as saliva, temperature changes, and patient habits may influence the effectiveness of denture cleansers in clinical conditions.

Further clinical studies are recommended to evaluate long-term effects and practical applicability.

CONCLUSION

Within the limitations of this *in vitro* study, all three denture cleansing agents demonstrated antimicrobial activity. Polident showed the highest efficacy, followed by Fittydent and Clinsodent. Denture cleansers can be recommended as an effective adjunct to mechanical cleaning methods for maintaining denture hygiene.

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